

Figure Supplementary 1. Hsp70 and AR protein abundance were not affected by IR or IPC-IR. Kidney of sham, IR and IPC-IR animals subject to 30 min of ischemia and 30 min of reperfusion (IR:30 min/30min) were processed and analyzed by western blot. **A-B.** Protein expression of Hsp70 in cortex (A) and medulla (B). **C-D** Protein expression of AR in cortex (C) and medulla (D). Western blots were normalized by β -actin. Bar graph represents mean \pm SEM (n=6 per group). Representative pictures are shown in the upper section.